

A Context-Aware Benchmarking Approach for Scenario-Based Evaluation of Smart Devices

Nikolaos Papadakis
Télécom SudParis / IP Paris
Paris, France
nikolaos.papadakis@telecom-
sudparis.eu

Krish Chatterjie
Télécom SudParis / IP Paris
Paris, France
chatterjie.krish@gmail.com

Roberto Yus
University of Maryland
Baltimore, Maryland, USA
ryus@umbc.edu

Athanasios Tsirikas
University of Patras
Patras, Greece
hanasis199782@gmail.com

Christian Badolato
University of Maryland, Baltimore
County
Baltimore, Maryland, USA
cbad1@umbc.edu

Kostas Magoutis
Computer Science Department
University of Crete
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
magoutis@ics.forth.gr

Fotios Fouskas
AEGIS IT RESEARCH
Athens, Greece
fotios.fouskas@gmail.com

Gregory Blanc
Télécom SudParis / IP Paris
Paris, France
gregory.blanc@telecom-sudparis.eu

Georgios Bouloukakis
University of Patras
Patras, Greece
Télécom SudParis / IP Paris
Paris, France
gbouloukakis@upatras.gr

Abstract

Understanding how smart devices behave under real-world conditions remains challenging, as existing benchmarking tools often isolate metrics like energy consumption or protocol compliance without considering realistic interactions or coordinated use. This paper presents a scenario-driven benchmarking framework tailored for smart devices which integrates control, orchestration, instrumentation, and monitoring into a unified, reproducible workflow. Our framework enables structured specification of interaction scenarios, precise scheduling of device actions, and synchronized measurement of energy usage and network activity. We validate our approach through a smart home testbed comprised of off-the-shelf speakers, lights, and fans across scenarios that reflect typical user interactions and adversarial network conditions. Results reveal behavioral differences not evident from device specifications alone, highlighting the importance of context-rich, scenario-based evaluation for understanding smart device performance in practice.

CCS Concepts

• **Computer systems organization** → **Embedded and cyber-physical systems**; • **Networks** → **Network measurement**; **Home networks**.

Keywords

Benchmarking, Smart Devices, Energy Profiling, Home Automation, Context-aware Systems, Network Traffic Analysis

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1 Introduction

As the Internet of Things (IoT) expands into homes, cities, and industrial environments, a wide variety of smart devices, from voice assistants and connected lighting to smart fans and security systems, are now deeply embedded in daily routines. These systems are no longer isolated sensors or actuators but complex, always-on platforms that respond to user interactions, automation routines, and unpredictable environmental inputs. Consider a home automation scenario: a user issues a voice command to turn off all devices before leaving the house. This single interaction may trigger a coordinated sequence involving multiple device types, protocols, and timing dependencies. Evaluating how such a sequence performs under real-world conditions (e.g., latency, energy usage, or network resilience) is essential for ensuring robust user experiences. However, assessing these behaviors remains difficult due to a lack of tools that account for real, coordinated, in-situ device usage.

Prior efforts have often approached this challenge through targeted studies of specific devices or behaviors. For example, Badolato et al. [7] analyze the network behavior of smart home devices to uncover traffic patterns and privacy risks. While such analyses offer valuable insights, they are typically labor-intensive, tailored to particular devices or setups, and difficult to generalize. The diversity of device brands, configurations, automation routines, and home environments makes it hard to reproduce these studies or

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apply their findings more broadly. To address this, benchmarking frameworks promise a more systematic and generalizable approach by offering structured workflows to evaluate device performance. Ideally, such benchmarks would allow researchers and developers to compare behaviors across different devices and scenarios, encouraging reproducibility and broader applicability. However, most existing benchmarking tools focus on narrow technical facets (such as microcontroller power consumption [11], protocol fuzzing [4, 8], or lab-based certification tests [23]) and lack support for scenario-driven, interactive evaluations. They rarely capture the real-world complexities of timing, coordination, and heterogeneity that define how smart devices behave in practice. For instance, knowing that a light bulb consumes 0.5W in idle tells us little about how it behaves when participating in a coordinated "wake-up" routine involving multiple devices and timing dependencies. Scenario-driven evaluations, by contrast, embed devices into realistic sequences (e.g., toggling a light, playing a voice command, and activating a plug in parallel) and capture emergent behaviors.

Developing a scenario-based benchmarking framework for smart devices is challenging due to the lack of standardized methods for coordinating heterogeneous devices, and capturing aligned measurements across different dimensions (e.g power, network, and state dimensions). Devices operate across diverse protocols (Wi-Fi, Zigbee) and often lack transparent APIs or consistent control mechanisms, complicating efforts to create reproducible, cross-device evaluations. Moreover, capturing realistic, user-like scenarios requires aligning control flows with environmental factors and instrumentation infrastructure, which existing tools do not support.

This paper introduces a scenario-driven benchmarking framework for smart devices that enables structured, reproducible experiments capturing smart device metrics under realistic, user-like scenarios. Unlike prior work, it integrates control, orchestration, instrumentation, and monitoring into a unified architecture capable of evaluating commodity devices within automated routines. We validate this approach through a smart home testbed featuring commercially available voice assistants, lighting devices, and smart fans. Our experiments explore device behavior during idle periods, user interactions, and network-layer attacks. The results highlight behavioral differences not evident from specifications alone but made visible through scenario-based evaluation. While our evaluation focuses on simplified scenarios, the framework lays the foundation for developers, researchers, and practitioners to better understand how smart devices operate in practice.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- (1) A scenario-driven benchmarking framework for structured and reproducible evaluation of smart device behavior under realistic conditions (Sect. 4).
- (2) A unified, context-aware architecture integrating device control, orchestration, instrumentation, and monitoring to capture performance metrics aligned with user-defined scenarios (Sect. 4).
- (3) A prototype implementation, *HAnalytics* (Sect. 5), validated through a smart home testbed, demonstrating how the framework reveals behavioral differences in energy use and network activity among smart devices (Sect. 6).

- (4) An open-source artifact containing measurement datasets, scenarios, and the prototype implementation to support reproducibility and future research [24].

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Sect. 2 reviews related work on IoT benchmarking and device evaluation. Sect. 3 introduces practical usage scenarios that motivate the need for structured benchmarking of smart devices. Finally, Sect. 7 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

2 Related Work

Research on benchmarking smart devices, and IoT systems, has largely concentrated on narrow axes of performance such as energy efficiency, protocol compliance, or firmware security. In this section, we review representative efforts across these dimensions and highlight how they fall short in characterizing full-stack device performance under realistic use.

Energy benchmarking has received sustained attention, particularly for evaluating the efficiency of low-power microcontrollers and radios under synthetic workloads. EEMBC's [11] benchmark suite including ULPMark [14], IoTMark-BLE [12], and IoTMark-Wi-Fi [13] provide precise, repeatable methods for comparing subsystem energy use across platforms, focusing on sleep modes, radio stacks, and sensor polling cycles under standardized conditions. While these tools offer valuable insight into component-level power behavior, they abstract away the control flows, automation triggers, and real-world usage patterns that shape end-to-end device performance. A more dynamic approach is offered by Thangarajan et al. [32], who introduce a distributed in-situ benchmarking framework for energy harvesting systems. Their system enables developers to evaluate how code changes affect runtime energy consumption across a live deployment. Though it captures power behavior in context and under real conditions, it remains focused on application logic.

Security-focused efforts such as BenchIoT [4] extend benchmarking into the firmware layer, quantifying the overheads of trusted execution environments and cryptographic primitives on resource-constrained platforms. These measurements are useful for understanding security-related trade-offs but are fundamentally limited to embedded code. Similarly, tools like IoTFuzzBench [8] and IoTBenchSL [9] standardize protocol fuzzing and firmware vulnerability detection workflows, focusing on crash detection, memory faults, or malformed input handling. These systems are optimized for stress-testing software components but are agnostic to how devices behave in practice when deployed as part of a connected environment. In parallel, tools such as IoTInspector [22] focus on network-level analysis of IoT devices to uncover privacy risks and communication patterns through passive observation of traffic flows. Commercial benchmarking and compliance platforms, such as Keysight's IoT Device Test platform [23], provide end-to-end protocol conformance testing and performance analysis. However, they typically operate as closed environments that focus on protocol correctness under ideal conditions, rather than the nuanced runtime behavior that arises when devices are embedded in usage scenarios with unpredictable control sequences, user input, or cross-device dependencies.

Attempts to model real-world usage have emerged in some academic work, albeit in constrained or virtualized settings. Schirrmeister et al. [28] propose a simulation-based testbed using Zephyr OS and QEMU to emulate embedded IoT devices for load testing a central Device Command and Control Infrastructure (DCCI). Their approach emphasizes performance benchmarking under configurable load and protocol conditions, and supports scenario definition and test automation through shell-based orchestration. However, the framework remains confined to virtualized environments and does not interface with physical devices or real-world measurement sources. It targets mainly backend scalability rather than device-level behavior.

Previous efforts provide valuable tools for evaluating specific aspects of hardware, firmware, or protocols but lack support for assessing how interconnected devices behave under realistic scenarios involving user routines, automation, and network stress. In particular, no prior work enables benchmarking multi-device interactions, such as a smart speaker triggering lighting and HVAC systems, while capturing aligned power, network, and timing data.

We address this gap with a scenario-driven benchmarking architecture that supports structured specification of realistic usage patterns across heterogeneous devices. Coordinated orchestration ensures precise control of device actions, while dedicated instrumentation captures device measurements. A shared context model aligns these measurements, enabling reproducible, system-level evaluation of behaviors such as automation sequences, cross-device dependencies, and resilience under adversarial conditions.

3 Motivating Scenarios

Modern smart environments integrate heterogeneous smart devices such as lighting fixtures, voice assistants, thermostats, cameras, each relying on different protocols and ecosystems. While vendor documentation typically reports functional specifications with precision (e.g., lumens, battery life, supported standards), operational behaviors that affect long-term performance and user experience are seldom disclosed. Key characteristics such as idle energy consumption, responsiveness to automation, background network activity, and resilience under load remain opaque.

Figure 1 illustrates this gap: specifications for a commercial smart speaker focus on physical dimensions, audio formats, and connectivity protocols but offer no guidance on power behavior during typical usage patterns or interaction latency under network stress. Such omissions are inconsequential for small installations but scale poorly. For example, consider a device that consumes just 1 Watt of power while idle. Across 500 devices, this results in 500 Watts of continuous draw. Over a month, this equates to $500 \text{ Watts} \times 24 \text{ hours/day} \times 30 \text{ days} = 360,000 \text{ Watt-hours} = 360 \text{ kWh}$. At an electricity rate of \$0.15 per kWh, this translates to \$54 per month solely for idle energy. These hidden costs accumulate quickly in larger deployments. Similarly, excessive background network activity, even if trivial per device, can congest shared wireless channels when scaled across dozens or hundreds of devices, degrading latency-sensitive functions such as real-time control or monitoring.

These challenges are representative of broader gaps in evaluating smart device behavior under real-world conditions. To illustrate

Example: Public Specifications for Google Home Smart Speaker [17]	
Dimensions	
Diameter: 3.79 in (96.4 mm)	Height: 5.62 in (142.8 mm)
Power cable: 70.8 in (1.8 m)	
Weight	
Device: 1.05 lbs (477 g)	Power adapter: 4.58 oz (130 g)
Colors	
Body: White	Base: Slate fabric
Supported Audio Formats	
HE-AAC, LC-AAC, MP3, Vorbis, WAV (LPCM), Opus, FLAC (24-bit/96 kHz)	
Wireless Network	
802.11b/g/n/ac (2.4 GHz or 5 GHz) Wi-Fi, Bluetooth 4.1: AVRCP, A2DP, GATT, GAP	
Speaker and Microphones	
2" driver + dual 2" passive radiators, 2 far-field mics with voice recognition	
Sensors	
Ambient light sensor, Capacitive touch controls	
Power and Ports	
Power: 16.5V, 2A Adapter: 100–240V, 1.1A Connectors: DC jack, Micro-USB (service only)	

Figure 1: Example of vendor specifications omitting operational behavior (e.g., idle power consumption, responsiveness).

the kinds of questions practitioners face and how structured benchmarking scenarios can help, we outline a set of practical, motivating scenarios that highlight common evaluation needs.

Scenario 1: Evaluating Energy Overhead in Standby States.

An infrastructure engineer must select smart lighting for a large office. Several devices offer similar functionality, but idle power consumption may differ significantly. Without empirical benchmarks, decisions rely on assumptions. A structured scenario toggles lights periodically and records energy use during idle and active periods, quantifying realistic standby overhead. Beyond procurement decisions, such benchmarking also supports optimizing existing deployments by identifying configurations that achieve an effective balance between illumination and energy consumption, helping reduce operational costs without compromising usability.

Scenario 2: Measuring Responsiveness under Routine Automation.

Automation sequences toggle devices in response to schedules or sensors. Variability in responsiveness affects user experience and control reliability. A scenario issues coordinated commands to devices at defined intervals, capturing response delays and performance under typical automation loads.

Scenario 3: Stress Testing Network Robustness.

Densely populated environments risk congestion from device chatter or attacks. Controlled stress scenarios (e.g., ICMP or UDP floods) reveal device resilience, packet loss, and service degradation during idle and active states.

These scenarios highlight the lack of structured, context-rich benchmarking for smart devices. Existing tools fail to capture operational dynamics under realistic use. In the next section, we introduce a scenario-driven benchmarking framework addressing these gaps through structured scenarios, precise orchestration, and synchronized measurement.

4 System Design

To support structured, context-aware evaluation of smart devices under realistic conditions, we introduce a scenario-first benchmarking architecture. The goal is to enable users, researchers, engineers, or system integrators to define usage scenarios, orchestrate experiments, collect relevant data, and analyze results in a reproducible and shareable format. Scenarios specify the operational context (e.g., idle, active, passive [7], stressed), the behavior under test (e.g., toggling lights, issuing voice commands), and the metrics of interest (e.g., power consumption, network activity, latency). This design cleanly decouples scenario specification from execution, enabling portable, repeatable studies across labs and device fleets. An overview of the architecture and workflow is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: High-level overview of the proposed benchmarking architecture.

Delivering structured, context-aware benchmarking requires an architecture capable of coordinating device actions, enforcing precise timing, and collecting aligned performance data under repeatable conditions. To this end, we designed a modular architecture composed of four interdependent layers: orchestration, control, instrumentation, and monitoring, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Each layer encapsulates distinct responsibilities, supporting flexibility, extensibility, and adaptability across diverse environments.

The control layer allows device control to be abstracted through a unified control interface supporting heterogeneous protocols and vendor ecosystems. Benchmarking scenarios are interpreted and scheduled by the orchestration layer, which manages timing and event sequencing. The instrumentation layer collects time-aligned measurements, including power metrics and packet traces. To safeguard experiment validity, the monitoring layer observes execution, detects failures, and enforces thresholds. All components share access to a centralized context model encoding device properties, relationships, and experimental history, enabling reproducible comparisons. Our implementation, *HAnalytics*, (see details in Sect. 5) is built atop Home Assistant (HA)[20], leveraging its extensive ecosystem for device control and metadata introspection, while maintaining a platform-agnostic design.

Consider **Scenario 1: Evaluating Energy Overhead in Standby States**, where an infrastructure engineer must assess smart lighting options for a high-traffic office corridor. Lights are toggled periodically to observe idle and active power consumption. Our framework executes this sequence through the automation infrastructure, captures energy use via in-line smart plugs, and records network traffic via passive capture nodes. The resulting data is enriched with precise timing, device states, and scenario metadata. When repeated

across devices, identical test conditions are ensured, enabling fair, side-by-side comparisons.

While our prototype leverages HA for orchestration and control, each architectural layer can be independently re-implemented with alternative tools, allowing adaptation to residential, commercial, or research deployments. The remainder of this section details each layer.

4.1 Orchestration Layer

The orchestration layer is responsible for interpreting benchmarking scenarios and coordinating their execution through precise, time-aligned control of devices. Scenarios describe sequences of actions, timing relationships, and involved devices, allowing benchmarking routines to reflect realistic usage patterns or stress conditions. The orchestration layer translates these high-level descriptions into ordered events.

Scenarios are typically expressed through structured configuration files, where users declare devices, desired actions, delays, and repetitions. These scenarios capture operational contexts such as routine automation, stress testing, or coordinated device inter-actions. The orchestration layer supports parallelism, sequential dependencies, randomized timing, and variable durations, enabling expressive modeling of complex behaviors.

Illustrative Example. Consider a simplified scenario modeling a typical morning routine in a smart home, for evaluating device network statistic and energy use across coordinated actions:

Listing 1: Illustrative Scenario: Morning Routine

```

scenario: Wake Up Routine
metrics:
  - power, network
sequence:
  - parallel:
    - action: light.turn_on
      target: bedroom_lights
      data:
        brightness: 50
        transition: 20s
    - action: switch.turn_on
      target: window_blinds
      data:
        duration: 30s
    - action: speaker.play
      target: smart_speaker
      data:
        prompt: "Play morning news"
  - delay: 90s
  - action: light.turn_off
    target: bedroom_lights
  
```

This scenario coordinates lighting, blinds, and a smart speaker in parallel, waits for a specified duration, and then turns the lights off. The orchestration layer interprets such scenarios, manages timing, ensures synchronization, and provides hooks for instrumentation to capture relevant metrics. To maintain flexibility across deployments, scenarios reference abstract device roles (e.g., `bedroom_lights`) resolved at runtime. This abstraction enables reusing scenarios across environments without requiring manual adjustment of specific device identifiers. Through structured orchestration, the architecture supports reproducible benchmarking workflows, capturing device behavior under controlled, context-rich conditions reflective of real-world usage.

Figure 3: Layered architecture for scenario-driven smart device benchmarking.

4.2 Control Layer

The control layer provides a unified interface through which the benchmarking framework interacts with physical and virtual smart devices. It is responsible for issuing commands, such as toggling lights, adjusting thermostats, or triggering media playback, and for abstracting the diversity of communication protocols, device ecosystems, and control paths present in modern smart environments. This abstraction enables scenario definitions to remain agnostic to specific devices or vendors, while ensuring that device interactions are consistent, repeatable, and aligned with scenario logic.

Smart devices vary widely in how they expose control interfaces. Some offer local APIs over protocols such as HTTP, MQTT, or CoAP. Others require interaction through vendor-specific bridges (e.g., Zigbee coordinators or Bluetooth proxies). Some depend on cloud-mediated control or integrations with external systems. The control layer absorbs this heterogeneity by providing a common, abstracted interface to the orchestration layer. This allows scenarios to invoke actions without requiring knowledge of device-specific mechanisms. To support realistic benchmarking scenarios, the control layer must accommodate both direct and indirect forms of device control. Direct control covers devices that can be accessed via network protocols or automation bridges. Indirect control addresses situations where devices require interaction through human-facing interfaces, such as voice assistants. In these cases, control actions may be delegated to auxiliary systems capable of issuing voice prompts, emulating remote controls, or interfacing with physical buttons. While deploying and configuring these auxiliary nodes requires some initial setup effort, these mechanisms are fully integrated into the benchmarking framework and transparent to the end user. Users define scenarios in a uniform way (e.g., YAML or graphical interface), without needing to distinguish between direct or indirect control path. Precision in timing is critical for benchmarking fidelity. The control layer does not manage timing autonomously but receives scheduled instructions from the orchestration layer. It is responsible for executing these instructions promptly and for ensuring that the intended sequence of actions is respected. Where delays occur due to network conditions or protocol latencies, precise logging enables such deviations to be accounted for during analysis. The control layer also interfaces with the system’s context

model to resolve abstract scenario targets into concrete device identifiers and appropriate control channels. For instance, a scenario targeting “bedroom lights” queries the context model to determine which devices fulfill that role and how to address them, whether through a local bridge, cloud API, or auxiliary control node. This abstraction simplifies scenario authoring and enhances portability. A single scenario definition can be applied across different environments, with the control layer dynamically resolving the appropriate targets and mechanisms to achieve the desired behaviors. If the target devices specified in a scenario do not exist in the current environment, the control layer raises an error during resolution.

4.3 Instrumentation Layer

The instrumentation layer is responsible for collecting performance-relevant data that defines a device’s operational behavior during benchmarking scenarios. It captures metrics (e.g. power consumption, network activity) and aligns these observations with scenario timelines, device actions, and environmental states. Instrumentation is passive and non-intrusive: the layer observes device behavior through external measurement tools without altering or probing device internals. Common data sources include in-line power meters for energy monitoring, network capture devices for traffic analysis, and logs of automation events. These sources operate independently but are synchronized to the benchmarking timeline, ensuring that measurements can be accurately attributed to specific scenario actions. The association between devices and measurement sources is managed through the system’s context model. For example, a smart bulb may be linked to a particular power meter and a local packet capture node. When a scenario is executed, the orchestration layer activates the relevant instrumentation according to these predefined associations. This allows a consistent infrastructure to support diverse scenarios without manual reconfiguration, while maintaining accurate mapping between devices, data sources, and experimental outcomes. All measurement components synchronize their clocks via NTP to a shared time source within the benchmarking environment, enabling precise alignment of events, actions, and observed effects. For example, a surge in network activity can be correlated with a specific light toggle in a scenario, while an energy anomaly can be traced to simultaneous device activations. Measurement start and stop times are explicitly bounded by the scenario execution window to ensure full coverage of the intended

observation period while excluding unrelated background activity. All collected data is annotated with structured metadata, including the type of metric, measurement source, device identity, and scenario parameters. This metadata supports reproducibility, facilitates comparisons across devices, and enables higher-level analysis of trends and anomalies. By separating measurement from control, the instrumentation layer ensures that observations are unbiased and do not interfere with device operation. This clean separation is critical for ensuring fairness, repeatability, accuracy and clarity when evaluating smart devices across a range of benchmarking scenarios.

4.4 Monitoring Layer

The monitoring layer provides real-time oversight of benchmarking execution, ensuring that scenarios proceed as defined and identifying anomalies that could compromise result validity. Unlike the instrumentation layer, which passively collects performance metrics for later analysis, the monitoring layer actively supervises scenario progression and validates adherence to timing and correctness constraints during runtime. Scenarios often encode assumptions about system behavior, such as requiring a light to react within a defined delay or expecting no packet loss during a scheduled sequence. The monitoring layer enforces these expectations by comparing observed system behavior to the scenario’s specifications. Deviations (like a device failing to respond, excessive delays, or missing triggers) can lead the monitoring layer to terminate the scenario early, annotate outputs with diagnostic information, or flag results as invalid. Monitoring integrates signals from multiple sources: acknowledgments from the control layer confirming command execution, feedback from instrumentation indicating abnormal conditions (e.g., unexpected power drops or network congestion), and internal progress checkpoints tied to the scenario’s timeline. These inputs are combined to provide a real-time assessment of scenario execution and adherence to expected behaviors. Ultimately, the monitoring layer safeguards benchmarking integrity by detecting deviations from expected execution and preventing misleading or invalid outcomes. It serves as a bridge between structured benchmarking plans and the dynamic realities of real-world smart environments, ensuring that results reflect genuine device performance under well-defined conditions.

4.5 Context Model

The context model maintains a structured, system-wide representation of devices, their attributes, their relationships to control and measurement infrastructure, and the history of prior benchmarking experiments. It serves as a persistent knowledge base that supports scenario execution, result interpretation, dataset labeling, and reproducibility.

Each device is characterized by static descriptors, such as vendor, model, supported protocols, and declared capabilities, alongside dynamic attributes like current state, physical location, and connectivity metadata. Additionally, the context model encodes relationships between devices and auxiliary infrastructure, identifying which endpoints are linked to energy meters, monitored by passive traffic sensors, or controlled via protocol bridges. During scenario execution, the context model resolves abstract roles into concrete targets.

For example, a reference to “Zigbee lights in the hallway” is dynamically mapped to specific devices based on their recorded properties and placement within the environment. This same mechanism ensures that data collection infrastructure is correctly associated with the devices under test, maintaining alignment between control actions and observation sources. All measurement data is automatically annotated using structured labels derived from the model. These include scenario ids, participating devices, operational states, and timestamps synchronized with scenario phases. Such labeling ensures datasets explicitly capture the conditions under which they were recorded, facilitating reuse for longitudinal studies or machine learning workflows. Benchmarking results are stored alongside full contextual metadata. This enables direct comparison of outcomes across time, environments, or device families while preserving the specific experimental conditions. The context model also supports retrospective queries and analysis. Practitioners can examine which tests have been applied to a device, analyze how results vary under different workloads, or assess scenario behavior across protocol ecosystems. Over time, this accumulated history enables dataset reuse, regression analysis, and traceability of behavioral trends.

5 Prototype Implementation: *HAnalytics*

We implement the *HAnalytics* prototype¹ atop HA [20], leveraging its rich integration ecosystem, automation capabilities, and support for heterogeneous smart devices. The prototype realizes the architecture described in the previous section through concrete instantiations of each architectural layer, using readily available hardware and software components.

Figure 4: Part of the *HAnalytics* prototype interface.

The orchestration layer is realized as a coordination service interfacing with HA via its WebSocket API. Benchmarking scenarios are defined through structured YAML files or selected interactively via a graphical frontend integrated into HA. As illustrated in Fig. 4, this interface allows users to visually select devices from a floor plan, specify operational contexts (e.g., idle, active, stressed states), and configure actions such as toggling lights, issuing voice commands, or triggering automation routines. Parameters like duration, frequency, and device states are explicitly defined. To support rapid experimentation and consistency, *HAnalytics* provides a library of

¹The prototype of *HAnalytics*, along with datasets, scenarios, and measurement artifacts, is available as part of our open-access artifact [24].

predefined scenarios reflecting common evaluation needs, such as measuring idle power over time, assessing responsiveness (end-to-end latency between a scenario trigger and the device-observable effect) under frequent toggling, or evaluating robustness under network stress. These scenarios can be directly used or adapted for specific environments. Once selected, scenarios are interpreted by the orchestrator, which coordinates precise execution through the control and instrumentation layers. All collected data is enriched with scenario metadata to ensure alignment across devices and iterations.

Device actuation is performed through HA’s native service interface, which abstracts interactions across Zigbee, Z-Wave, Wi-Fi, and vendor-specific APIs. For devices that cannot be directly controlled, for example smart speakers requiring audio prompts, *HAnalytics* employs remote control nodes (typically Raspberry Pi devices) positioned near the targets. These nodes execute scripts or play audio files in synchronization with the benchmarking schedule. Additionally, the control layer supports scenarios evaluating resilience under adverse network conditions via an integrated attack module capable of launching ICMP flood [19], SYN flood [29], and UDP flood [30] attacks. These are executed by dedicated nodes, triggered by the orchestrator. This infrastructure enables comprehensive assessment of device robustness, failure behavior, and recovery latency under controlled interference.

The instrumentation layer collects performance metrics aligned with scenario timelines. Power consumption is measured using smart plugs (e.g., TP-Link HS110, Shelly Plug S) exposing real-time data via APIs. For devices without inline monitoring, external sensors are associated through the context model. Network activity is captured via an OpenWRT router configured for targeted packet captures, filtered by device MAC addresses to ensure data relevance and reduce overhead. Captures are timestamped, annotated with scenario metadata, and stored for analysis. Additional monitoring is performed by passive sniffers (ESP32 nodes or Raspberry Pis), recording MAC-layer traffic in sync with scenario triggers. Measurements are synchronized across data sources and linked to device identities, enabling precise attribution of observed behaviors.

The monitoring layer provides runtime oversight, recording device states, scenario progress, and external observations. In its current form, monitoring is passive: deviations from expected behavior (e.g., delayed responses or unresponsive devices) are logged but require user intervention for resolution. State tracking relies on HA’s entity model, capturing discrete updates with timestamps. While sufficient for post-hoc analysis, this approach does not enforce formal state correctness during execution. Future extensions could adopt formal models (e.g., FSMs) for real-time validation and adaptive control in response to anomalies.

All layers interact with a centralized context repository, built atop HA’s entity registry and extended with additional metadata. This repository maintains mappings between devices, locations, measurement sources, and prior experiments. It enables the orchestrator to resolve abstract scenarios into concrete execution plans and ensures consistent alignment of control and observation paths across experiments.

6 Experimental Results

This section demonstrates how *HAnalytics* enables structured evaluation of smart devices through realistic, scenario-driven experimentation. Rather than evaluating the benchmark in isolation, we focus on how *HAnalytics* supports practical analysis of device behavior across energy consumption and resilience to network stress, aligned with the motivating scenarios from Section 3.

Our evaluation focuses on two questions: (1) Can *HAnalytics* reliably capture synchronized, multi-modal measurements, such as the one described in the motivating scenarios? (2) What behavioral differences or anomalies emerge when smart devices operate under orchestrated conditions? The experiments map to the following motivating scenarios, showcasing *HAnalytics*’s ability to reveal operational characteristics not visible through datasheets alone. **Scenario 1:** Evaluating Energy Overhead in Standby States. We measured idle and active power draw across lighting devices to quantify realistic standby overhead and inform energy-conscious decisions. **Scenario 2:** Stress Testing Network Robustness. We subjected devices to controlled network-layer stress (ICMP, SYN, UDP floods), monitoring packet loss, latency, and behavioral degradation. We begin with the experimental setup, detailing the devices tested, measurement infrastructure, and scenario design, followed by key results.

6.1 Experimental Setup

To assess real-world smart device behavior under various operational and stress conditions, we constructed a smart home testbed (see Figure 5). It comprises heterogeneous consumer-grade devices, programmable measurement and control infrastructure using the *HAnalytics* prototype, and scenario orchestration scripts. The setup integrates energy monitoring, network capture, and behavior logging into a unified benchmarking environment. A *Netgear WAX206* router [25], flashed with *OpenWRT 23.0* [26], serves as the main network gateway, providing 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi connectivity to smart devices and connecting via Ethernet to backend infrastructure and a Zigbee bridge. A *Philips Hue Bridge* [31], connected over Ethernet, manages Zigbee-based bulbs. An *HA node*, implemented on a Raspberry Pi 4B running *Home Assistant OS 15.2* with Core 2025.6.1 [21], coordinates device states and orchestrates automation sequences via supported APIs. To evaluate interactions under fault conditions, two additional Raspberry Pi nodes are employed: An *Attacker Pi*, which launches network stressors (ICMP, SYN, UDP floods), a *Control Node Pi*, which issues repeatable synthetic audio prompts for controlled voice-triggered testing. Measurements are collected on a *desktop Ubuntu 22.04.1* server, which mounts NFS shares from the OpenWRT router to retrieve packet captures and logs, and controls the testbed configuration via the router’s administrative interface.

The testbed incorporates three core device types reflecting common categories in residential automation: smart speakers (*Google Nest Mini* [15], *Amazon Echo Dot* [5]), smart lighting (*Philips Hue* [27], *Amazon Basics bulbs* [6]), and Internet-connected tower fans (*Govee H7102* [18], *Dreo Circulator* [10]). Devices are configured via their native mobile apps and integrated into *HAnalytics* for centralized control. While our system supports fully automated voice-triggered scenarios via audio playback on auxiliary nodes (e.g., the Voice

Figure 5: Experimental testbed setup.

Control Pi), for the experiments presented in this paper, we manually issued voice commands to the assistants. Toggling commands for other devices were automated through HA’s WebSocket API as part of the defined scenarios. Devices were evaluated in operational states representing typical interactions or idle behavior, which also answers the questions of the motivating scenarios.

To evaluate both routine operation and resilience, we defined the following device states:

Idle: Devices powered and connected but not actively interacted with.

Active: Devices triggered via automation or voice commands.

Attack – ICMP Flood: Continuous ICMP requests.

Attack – SYN Flood: SYN packets.

Attack – UDP Broadcast: Broadcast traffic.

Each experiment ran for controlled durations of both 1 minute and 5 minutes across all operational states. Logging was synchronized across components; power was measured via inline meters, and packet captures were timestamped and stored for post-processing at the router. This multi-modal instrumentation enables correlation of control inputs with observable network and energy behavior under varying loads.

6.2 Results Overview

We present results from controlled benchmarking scenarios. Our aim is twofold: (1) to demonstrate *HAnalytics*’s ability to collect synchronized, multi-modal measurements, and (2) to uncover behavioral patterns under orchestrated conditions. Each scenario produced time-aligned traces of power draw, device state transitions, and network activity. These traces yield interpretable metrics such as transmission rates, network usage, and average power consumption under specific workloads. The scenario-first methodology enables direct device comparisons under identical triggers and timing, making deviations meaningful rather than anecdotal.

The three benchmark scenarios (*Idle*, *Active*, *ICMP Flood*, *SYN Flood*, and *UDP Broadcast*) exposed expected behavioral differences across the six devices. Fig. 6 (A) shows average power consumption across states. The Google Nest Mini shows stable consumption, increasing modestly from 1.5 W at idle to 1.9 W during interaction. In contrast, the Echo Dot v5 jumps from 1.3 W to 2.7 W, aligning with community measurements placing Nest Mini usage below 2 W [3] despite a 15 W adapter [16]. While we did not replicate full-volume playback scenarios, *HAnalytics* readily enables users to

Figure 6: (A) Average power consumption across states; (B) Network-layer metrics across evaluated scenarios.

benchmark specific workloads, e.g., to assess powerbank suitability. For smart lighting, measured consumption fell below datasheet maximums (9 W nominal for both Philips Hue White A19 [2] and Amazon Basics [1]). The Zigbee Hue bulb idles near 8 W, averaging 4.6 W while dimming. The Wi-Fi Amazon bulb idles at 3.8 W, rising to 4.2 W during color cycling. These results confirm datasheet wattages represent upper bounds rather than realistic consumption and highlight the need for scenario-driven benchmarking.

On the network side (Fig. 6 (B)), the smart speakers show the most activity during *Active* scenarios, averaging 34 packets per second with 700 B payloads, reflecting cloud-based assistant behavior. Lighting devices differ sharply: the Zigbee Hue bulb communicates minimally through its bridge, while the Wi-Fi Amazon bulb emits over triple the packets during color changes. Fans produce negligible traffic despite active toggling. Under adversarial load, network metrics align with expectations: packet rates spike beyond 0.5 million per minute, with bitrates near 8 Mbit./s. While devices remained reachable during flood scenarios, capture processes for some smart speakers terminated prematurely due to buffer exhaustion, not device failure. Under UDP flooding, lighting devices occasionally failed to toggle, and smart speakers exhibited delays. Performance degradation manifested as increased latency rather than disconnection. No catastrophic failures occurred, but resilience thresholds emerged through controlled, sustained testing. These findings underscore the value of benchmarking devices within realistic scenarios. Seemingly minor differences in idle consumption matter in battery-backed or portable contexts. Likewise, the unpredictability of network behavior during routine actions cannot be inferred from datasheets alone. Through structured, scenario-driven benchmarking, *HAnalytics* enables developers and users to surface nuanced behaviors, and answer practical deployment questions which are otherwise opaque. The full dataset, including pcap traces and measurement logs is provided as part of our open-access artifact [24].

7 Conclusions

Smart devices are increasingly embedded in everyday environments, yet systematic methods for evaluating their behavior under realistic conditions remain limited. In this work, we introduced a scenario-driven benchmarking framework that unifies control, observation, and measurement within a single setup. Rather than

isolating metrics such as component-level energy consumption, our approach emphasizes contextual evaluation, examining how devices respond to real-world triggers, automation routines, and stress conditions. Through a prototype implementation and testbed evaluation with commodity smart home devices, we demonstrated how scenario-based analysis can reveal subtle yet important behavioral differences. Devices offering similar user-facing functions frequently exhibited divergent network or energy characteristics and varying resilience under adversarial conditions. These findings underscore the value of grounding benchmarks in realistic usage contexts, where specification sheets fail to capture operational nuances. By enabling structured, repeatable experiments that align device behavior with synchronized measurement and rich metadata, our system lays a foundation for more transparent and practical evaluation of smart devices.

Looking ahead, we aim to extend this approach to other IoT domains beyond the smart home. Achieving this will require adapting scenarios to reflect the distinct operational contexts and challenges of different IoT domains, where devices may encounter different triggers, constraints, and failure modes. Expanding into these areas will further validate the flexibility of scenario-driven benchmarking and broaden its relevance to a wider range of IoT applications.

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